

**THE HISTORY OF TERMINATING CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS AND
REHABILITATION INSTITUTIONS WITHOUT RESOLVING THE
ISSUE OF CULPABILITY**

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The criminal procedure system of Central Asian states is historically closely linked to the legal traditions of the Russian Empire. The formation of legislation in this region occurred as a result of the introduction and subsequent development of the Russian legal system. Specifically, this process, which began in the mid-19th century, was implemented through the legal norms and practices of the Russian Empire.

On August 15, 1845, the Russian Empire adopted the "Statute of Criminal and Corrective Punishments," which was a significant milestone in the history of Russian criminal legislation and had a considerable impact on Central Asia. This statute clearly defined the possibilities and conditions for abandoning criminal prosecution. In modern criminal procedural terminology, this statute identified two main groups for terminating criminal cases:¹

The first group is characterized by circumstances that exclude criminal liability. The law specifies the following six instances:

¹ См.: Российское законодательство X-XX вв. В эт. Т. 6. С. 163 <https://www.prlib.ru/item/1874387>

1. An action that led to accidental and unexpected consequences but is not actually a crime;
2. Early childhood, meaning the age at which the defendant is incapable of understanding the nature of their actions;
3. Conditions leading to loss of reason, mental illness, or loss of consciousness;
4. A mistake made due to chance or deception;
5. Coercion under the influence of irresistible force;
6. Necessary defense.

Examining these instances allows us to highlight their common features. Firstly, these rules indicate that a crime was not committed due to the absence of certain elements of the crime. Secondly, the statement that "the committed act should not be attributed to the offender" does not prevent an investigation to establish these circumstances. Thirdly, these circumstances (perhaps excluding point 5) are recognized as grounds for rehabilitation and exonerate the person.²

The second group includes:

1. Death of the offender;
2. Reconciliation with the victim;
3. Expiration of the statute of limitations;
4. Pardon and forgiveness of offenders.

A separate group was established for circumstances that exclude criminal prosecution applicable to individuals with immunity from criminal liability.

According to researchers S. Makhmudov and N. Abdurakhmanov, the legislation of

² 1 См.: Сафронов Д.М. Обстоятельства, исключающие уголовное преследование: Дис... канд. юрид. наук. Омск, 2003. С. 50-51. https://rusneb.ru/catalog/000199_000009_002610653/

the Russian Empire was the starting point for legal reforms in the Central Asian region, and it was from this stage that the principles of abolishing or mitigating criminal liability were formed.³

The criminal procedural norms introduced in Central Asia under the influence of Russian legislation were adapted to local conditions. In the early 20th century, these legal norms became more complex under Soviet legislation, and during the independence period, Central Asian states revisited this experience in creating their national legislation. This historical stage laid the foundation for the continuous development of legal institutional structures in the current criminal procedural systems of Central Asian states.

Article 160 of the "Statute of Criminal and Corrective Punishments," adopted in 1845, provided for "reconciliation with the victim" as one of the grounds for exemption from punishment. However, this was only applied to cases initiated based on the victim's complaint. Such cases are specified in Article 171.⁴

According to the Criminal Procedure Statute (UUS) of 1864, the criminal procedure system was organized in such a way that all final decisions were made by the court. These decisions also included the "Resolution on the Termination of Criminal Prosecution," which I.Ya. Foynitsky described as follows: "A court decision whereby it is deemed impossible to continue considering the indictment in court, and all measures taken against the accused are canceled." Criminal procedural legislation allows for the division of circumstances that exclude criminal prosecution

³ <https://uzlaw.uz/ilmiy-ishlar/reabilitatsiya-asoslariga-kora-jinoyat-ishini-tugatishning-ayrim-jihatlari/>

⁴ З См.: Российское законодательство X-XX вв.: В т. 9. Судебная реформа. Т. 6. М., 1991. С. 322-323.
<https://www.prlib.ru/item/1874389>

into several groups, but these norms are scattered throughout the text of the law. In 1903, leading scholars of the time, N.D. Sergiyevsky, N.S. Tagantsev, N.A. Neklyudov, and I.Ya. Foynitsky developed a new "Criminal Code." In the process of preparing this document, these scholars made significant contributions to reforming and improving the criminal legislation of their time. As a result of their work, a number of important aspects necessary for establishing criminal liability were clarified in the legislation. Specifically, age limits for criminal liability were clearly defined, criteria for assessing a person's mental state were developed, and legal norms that serve as the basis for exemption from criminal liability in certain cases were systematized.⁵ These efforts represented an important step in aligning criminal legislation with modern requirements.

However, despite these progressive legal approaches, the 1903 Criminal Code did not come into full force. This was due to the strengthening of autocratic rule in Russia at that time. The political conditions hindering the development of an independent legal system prevented the widespread implementation of this code in practice. Therefore, the advanced legal concepts reflected in this regulation were not fully realized in their time and were only highly appreciated in theory.

The Fundamentals of Criminal Procedure of the USSR and Union Republics (hereinafter referred to as the Fundamentals of Criminal Procedure), adopted in 1958, significantly changed the list of grounds for terminating criminal proceedings. This document began to more realistically reflect various situations that prevent the continuation of criminal proceedings or indicate the inadvisability of continuing

⁵ Фойницкий И.Я. Курс уголовного судопроизводства. Т. 2. СПб., 1996. С. 55.

criminal prosecution of the accused. Article 5 of the Fundamentals of Criminal Procedure replaced Article 4 of the 1923 RSFSR Criminal Procedure Code. It listed the following circumstances that preclude criminal proceedings or their continuation:

1. The absence of a criminal event;
2. The absence of corpus delicti in the action;
3. Expiration of the statute of limitations;
4. An act of amnesty, if it excludes the application of punishment for the committed act, as well as pardon of certain persons;
5. Not having reached the age of criminal responsibility according to the law at the time of committing a socially dangerous act;
6. Reconciliation of the victim with the accused in cases established by the legislation of the union republics;
7. The absence of a complaint from the victim, if the case can be initiated only on the basis of their complaint, except in cases where the legislation of the union republics gives the prosecutor the right to initiate a case even without a complaint from the victim;
8. Death of a person, except in cases where the criminal case is necessary to acquit the deceased person or to reopen the case against other persons due to newly discovered circumstances;
9. The existence of a court verdict that has entered into legal force against a person on the same charge.

According to the Decree of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the RSFSR dated May 8, 1968, Parts 1 and 2 of Article 402 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the

RSFSR (CPC) were restated in a new edition. According to these changes, the court was also given the right to terminate a criminal case against a minor and apply educational measures. This right could be exercised by the court in the process of considering the criminal case on its merits.

In 1977, as a result of introducing a new basis for administrative liability into criminal legislation (Article 50 of the Criminal Code of the RSFSR), Article 62 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the RSFSR was supplemented with a clause on "Termination of a criminal case in connection with the application of administrative penalties." This provision began to be actively applied by preliminary investigation bodies. By the Decree of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the RSFSR dated August 8, 1983, another new basis for terminating a criminal case was introduced. According to it, paragraph 10 was added to Article 5 of the Criminal Procedure Code, establishing the following rule: If the decision of the investigative body, prosecutor, or inquiry body to terminate the criminal case on the same charge has not been canceled, the criminal case shall be terminated.

In order to regulate situations encountered in practice, during the consideration of a criminal case, if a criminal law adopted after the commission of the crime abolished the criminality and punishment of this act before the court verdict entered into legal force, the criminal case should have been terminated. In this regard, in accordance with the Law of the RSFSR of December 5, 1991, Article 5 of the Criminal Procedure Code was supplemented with a new Part 2. It was worded as follows: "If the criminal law adopted after the commission of the crime abolishes the criminality and punishment of this act before the court verdict enters into legal force, a criminal case shall not be initiated or the initiated case shall be terminated."

References;

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